

As part of our Master's thesis at Blekinge Institute of Technology, our research investigates how developers and maintainers perceive vulnerabilities in FOSS/OSS dependencies they include in their projects. Considering that software supply chain attacks have become more frequent in recent years, understanding how developers' awareness of the risks linked to having vulnerable dependencies in their dependency trees is vital for the open-source community and the global software development community that relies on FOSS/OSS, as well as for the users of software supported by FOSS/OSS. Your participation in this research will help us understand how developers manage dependencies in their projects. The study focuses on developers from these ecosystems and web frameworks: Python (Django), JavaScript (Next.js), Java (Spring Boot), PHP (Laravel), and Ruby (Ruby on Rails).

Participation in this research is entirely voluntary, and you can withdraw from the interview at any time. We will not retain any personal data or identifiable information. Your name, role, email address, and any identifiable details will not be published or shared with anyone. You can skip any questions you are not comfortable answering. Your responses will remain anonymous and will not be linked to the project(s) you represent. The interviews will be recorded and kept for the duration of the study to allow the supervisor to verify the authenticity of the reported data, after which they will be deleted.

Questions

- 1. Please introduce yourself and the project(s) you are a developer, contributor, or maintainer of. (Projects based on the main framework are also accepted, e.g., a maintainer or contributor for django-debug-toolbar but not Django itself, or if you develop using Django).**

For this, you can mention the project(s), how long you have been involved with it/them, and how you contribute to it, that is, are you a developer, maintainer, contributor, owner, admin, etc. This is meant to help us get to know you without you having to provide any identifying personal information. Also, mention your job title.

- 2. What is your role in the project(s)?**

Options can be: Contribute code, Tester, Triage issues to accept tickets, Review pull requests, Merge pull requests, Decide on software design, Decide on security issues

3. How is the project(s) you are working on governed?

Options can be: Corporate company; A non-profit foundation; Community-driven, with a registered non-profit foundation; Community-driven without a registered foundation/corporate company; Corporate company is managing the FOSS/OSS project; Creators or maintainers (a few individuals)

4. Are there any governance structures or teams within your project responsible for security issues within your project?

This is a follow-up to the question regarding the project's governance. For example, some projects have separate technical boards/steering councils and security teams. You can share details on those structures and share which ones you participate in.

5. From which ecosystem do(es) your project(s) belong to?

Options are: Python, Java, JavaScript, PHP, Ruby

6. Which web framework do(es) your project(s) belong to?

Options are: Django, Spring Boot, Next.js, Laravel, Ruby on Rails

7. How many years of experience do you have with the framework?

8. Which other ecosystems does your project rely on?

Python, Java, JavaScript, PHP, Ruby – if you use dependencies from other ecosystems.

9. How are security issue reports managed in your project(s)?

The question seeks to understand how your project handles security reports within the project(s) you maintain for vulnerabilities discovered within your project(s). This question focuses on the vulnerabilities in your project code or CI/CD scripts for infrastructure definitions, and how they are handled from the time they are reported through their resolution and publication as CVEs.

10. How conscious are you of the dangers that vulnerable dependencies present to your projects?

**11. How aware are you of supply chain attacks and their effects on projects?
How conscious are you of the risks that dependencies create in relation to supply chain threats?**

12. How do you identify dependencies with vulnerabilities within your projects?

The question seeks to understand which tools or automation your projects have in place to identify vulnerable dependencies. It also seeks to understand how you become aware of CVEs published by the dependencies you use in your project. FOSS/OSS projects can also be taken over by malicious actors, who may use them to launch supply chain attacks.

13. What influences the decision to update to newer versions of the dependencies within your projects?

The question seeks to understand the decision-making process for upgrading dependencies from pinned versions when vulnerabilities are discovered.

14. How do you track the maintenance of dependencies in your projects?

This question aims to understand whether developers oversee dependencies within their projects. Some dependencies become outdated and abandoned, and their vulnerabilities are never addressed.

15. How do you handle vulnerable dependencies within your project?

This question seeks to understand whether vulnerable dependencies are always updated and what happens when there is no newer version to upgrade to.

16. How long does it take to update vulnerable dependencies within your projects?

This question seeks to understand the resolution times, from the moment a dependency is identified as vulnerable to the time an upgrade or removal is performed.

17. How do you handle vulnerable dependencies that are no longer being maintained?

It is common for FOSS/OSS projects to become unmaintained. This question seeks to understand how developers handle dependencies that are no longer maintained.

18. For dependencies within your ecosystem, taking over abandoned projects which you have as dependencies and heavily rely on may be a consideration. How difficult is this when the dependency is outside of your ecosystem? For example, a deprecated JavaScript library used in a Django project.

19. What practices and tools are in place for supply chain attacks mitigation for your projects?

This question seeks to understand current practices for mitigating supply chain attacks through project dependencies in FOSS/OSS.

20. Have any of the projects you have worked on ever been exposed to supply chain attacks?

21. What factors help you to address vulnerable dependencies within your projects?

22. What challenges do you face which hinder you in addressing vulnerable dependencies within your projects?

23. What recommendations do you have for FOSS/OSS dependency management to mitigate supply chain attacks?

24. Do you have anything else you might want to add with regard to dependency management in FOSS/OSS projects to ensure FOSS/OSS security?